

SLOT LOADED PATCH ANTENNA FOR COMMUNICATION IN S-BAND

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Abstract:

A suitable dual frequency antenna should have resembling characteristics in both operating forms (transmitting and receiving) in terms of return loss, radiation properties and impedance matching. A single tunable antenna eliminates the need for multiple antennas for operation in multiple frequency bands. In this paper, a study of rectangular patch antenna with variations in structure by introduction of slots of different shapes on the patch surface is carried out to investigate the shift in resonant frequency/ frequencies for applications such as dual frequency operations in S band using high frequency simulation software CST Microwave Studio and followed by fabrication and measurement using VNA network analyzer. The overall dimension of the patch is kept the same to avoid extra space and modifications are carried out within the dimension of the original patch. The results obtained with these simulated and measured values are shown good dual frequency responses in the S band.

1. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, several methods for obtaining dual-band, multiband and/or wideband antenna characteristics have been developed [1, 2, and 9]. Communication system applications such as radar, synthetic aperture radar (SAR), and many other applications etc. often require dual frequency patch antennas to avoid the use of two different antennas[3,4].

In this, a study of probe feed micro strip rectangular patch antenna with various designs is done [7]. Patch antenna with variations in structure by introduction of slots of different shapes on the surface is carried out to investigate the shift in resonant frequency/ frequencies for applications such as dual frequency operations [2, 5, and 6]. Also tuning frequency/ frequencies within the same band is investigated. Simulations of basic rectangular patch antenna and structural modifications of the basic patch using high frequency software CST Microwave Studio are carried out.

The antenna is fabricated and characterized for its return loss (RL), gain, VSWR, and radiation patterns. The results obtained with these simulated and measured values are summarized in the preceding section

2. PLANAR PATCH BEFORE THE INTRODUCTION OF SLOT AND SLITS

A planer patch antenna is designed (without structural modification) Figure 1 shows the basic structure of a coaxially fed rectangular micro strip antenna (RMSA).

Figure 1: Coaxially fed rectangular patch antenna

A simple micro strip patch antenna has been designed using the following specifications (table 1)

Table 1: Design specifications of the basic patch

SL. No	Parameter	Dimension
1	Length of ground plane(Lg)	54mm
2	Width of ground plane(Wg)	62m
3	Length of Patch(Lp)	32mm
4	Width of Patch(Wp)	42 mm
5	Dielectric constant	4.8
6	Substrate height	1.5 mm

3. SIMULATION FOR OPTIMIZED FEED POINT LOCATION OF SIMPLE ANTENNA

A simple micro strip rectangular patch antenna has been shown in Figure 1. To select the feeding port location of the patch antenna, number of simulations has been performed and the optimized value has been selected. Among all the values feed point at the location 5 mm from the center towards the radiating edge along the X axis showed maximum return loss value i.e. RL of -51.67 dB and good dual frequency response has been found at the feeding point 3 mm along the X axis. The results are summarized in the following table 1 and plotted in figure2.

Table 2: Frequency (GHz) versus Return Loss (dB) at different feeding point locations

Feed point Location from Center(mm)	Frequency -1 (GHz)	Return Loss(dB)	Frequency-2 (GHz)	Return Loss(dB)
0	2.228	-32.90	3.515	-23.04
1	2.225	-35.34	3.509	-24.70
2	2.225	-35.24	3.506	-28.28
3	2.228	-32.45	3.506	-41.65
4	2.225	-31.44	3.503	-22.85
5	2.225	-51.67	3.5	-16.11
6	2.225	-38.72	3.5	-11.71
7	2.228	-31.41	3.79	-8.52
8	2.222	-43.93	3.79	-10.34
9	2.225	-35.13	3.8	-10.908
10	2.222	-34.36	3.79	-10.00

Figure 2: Frequency (GHz) Versus Return Loss (dB) for the simple Patch

4. MODIFICATION OF BASIC PATCH

The simple patch has been modified by inserting slots on the patch. First, some slots (figure 3) have been put on the patch using CST Microwave Studio. The slots are cut in two plus-sign shape as indicated in Figure 3 and these slots position are shifting along the X axis and a fixed slot of 2 mm width, 20 mm long is vertically inserted at a distance $X=14$ mm. By shifting the slots in X direction, towards the radiating edge, the results of shift in frequency and its respective return loss have been observed and tabulated in table 3.

From the simulation, it has been observed that the slots position as varied along the X axis, as the upper slot position at $X=4$ mm and lower slot position at $X=6$ mm i.e. $X=(4, 6)$ and the feeding point port location is at 5 mm towards the radiating edge, the best result with a RL value of -27.61 dB is obtained with a slight change of resonant frequency (from 2.225 GHz to

2.237 GHz). It is also observed that for few of particular slots position the antenna shows dual tuning.

The different structures with their slot position are shown in Figure 3 (Structure i to Structure x)

Figure 3: shows the different antenna structures (From i to x)

Structure (i) $X = (-8, -8\text{mm})$

Structure (iii) $X = (0, 2)$

Structure (vii) $X = (4, 6)$

Structure (viii) $X = (-8, 0)$

Structure (ix) $X = (-4.2)$

Structure (x) X= (-8,-8)

In this way, every location of these plus shape slots are shifted along the X - axis and the results are summarized in the table 3 and plotted in the graph (figure 4).

Table 3: Return Loss vs. Position of the Slots

Slot Positions X(A,B)	Frequency-1	Return Loss	Frequency -2	Return Loss
0,2	2.237	-27.31	3.515	-13.02
0,4	2.237	-27.34	3.515	-12.934
0,6	2.24	-26.05	3.515	-12.00
0,8	2.246	-21.85	3.533	-12.99
4,6	2.237	-27.61	3.518	-12.78
4,-2	2.237	-25.78	3.518	-12.536
4,-4	2.237	-25.81	3.515	-12.50
4,-6	2.237	25.76	3.518	-12.56
4,-8	2.237	-25.19	3.518	-12.643
4,0	2.237	-27.34	3.515	-12.934
-8,0	2.24	-26.00	3.518	-12.08

Figure 4: Frequency (GHz) Vs. Return loss for different slot position

From the above table it is observed that the slots position at X= (4, 6) results maximum RL value of -27.61 dB at frequency 2.237 GHz.

5. SIMULATION FOR OPTIMIZATION OF FEED POINT LOCATION OF SLOTTED ANTENNA

Now selecting the above patch Structure (vii) with slot X= (4, 6) the feeding point location is further shifted by 1 mm in step from the center along + ve X axis towards the radiating edge to observe the best responses of frequency and its respective return loss and results are shown in figure 5 and summarized in the table4 as given below.

Figure: 5: Frequency (GHz) versus Return Loss (dB) for the structure X(4,6)

Table 4: Table shows the Return Loss at different feeding point with slot X (4, 6)

Deferent Feeding Point	Frequency 1	Return Loss 1	Frequency 2	Return Loss2
1	2.24	-29.32	3.521	-29.81
2	2.24	-28.85	3.531	-25.46
3	2.24	-27.25	3.531	-18.46
4	2.237	-32.67	3.515	-17.77
5	2.237	-27.61	3.518	-12.78
6	2.234	-30.51	3.518	-10.64
7	2.237	-26.44	3.749	-8.31
8	2.237	-25.11	3.749	-8.38
9	2.237	-23.41	3.749	-8.70
10	2.234	-20.34	3.755	-8.22

From the table 4, the maximum return loss is -32.67 dB has been observed at frequency 2.237 GHz and also obtained dual frequency responses with another return loss value is – 17.77 dB at frequency 3.515 GHz. for the feeding point location at 4 mm from the center towards the radiating edge.

Figure 6: Geometrical diagram of slot loaded patch with best Matching, Structure (vii), X (4, 6)

6. MEASUREMENT OF RADIATION PATTERN AND GAIN

The simulated radiation pattern and its gain at frequency 2.5 GHz is shown in figure 7. From the VSWR plot (figure 8), it has been seen that the value of VSWR is 1.145 at frequency 2.237 GHz.

Figure 7: Radiation pattern at frequency 2.5 GHz (Simulated)

Figure 8: VSWR plot at 2.237 GHz (Simulated)

7. FABRICATION AND MEASUREMENTS

The antenna is fabricated (figure 9) and measured various performance characteristics (such as return loss, VSWR, radiation pattern, and gain) using a vector network analyzer. The results are summarized as follows:

Figure 9: Top and Bottom view of the fabricated antenna (Structure vii)

(i) Top view (ii) Bottom view

Figure 10: Measured Frequency (GHz) versus Return Loss (dB) using VNA

Table 5: Comparison of Simulated versus Measured results

Slotted Antenna	Simulated Result- 1	Measured Result-1	Simulated Result -2	Measured Result-2
Operated frequency (GHz)	2.237	2.915	3.515	3.905
Return Loss (dB)	-32.67	-33.537	-17.77	-17.286

Figure 10 shows the measured plot for structure vii. The above table (table 5) shows the simulated results using CST Microwave Studio and fabricated measured results using VNA. (Vector Network Analyzer)

Figure 11: Frequency vs. Return loss of the fabricated antenna

Figure 12: Simulation results Frequency vs. Return loss of the antenna

Figure 13: Comparison of measured results versus simulated results

8. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

From the above table 5, it is seen that from measured results (using VNA), at lower frequencies the frequency is shifting from 2.237 GHz to 2.915 GHz with an increased RL from -32.67 dB to -33.537dB. On the other hand in the higher frequency range, the resonant frequency changes from 3.515 GHz to 3.905 GHz with return loss value at -17.286 dB. The gain of the measured value of the fabricated antenna is 4.022 dB and 8.109 dB at frequencies 2.915 GHz and 3.905 GHz respectively. The comparative graph of simulated result versus fabricated measured results of the antenna is plotted in figure 13 and the plot of the radiation pattern is shown in figure 14. This Plus Sign Shape Slot loaded patch antenna can be applicable for dual frequency application in S band.

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